

A Geospatial Analysis of Work From Home Policies on UK Job Satisfaction During Covid-19

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Summary

This study fills a research gap in understanding how enforced Work From Home (WFH) has affected job satisfaction across different regions in the United Kingdom. By analysing data from the UK Household Longitudinal Study alongside a dedicated COVID-19 survey, the study uncovers notable differences in job satisfaction tied to geographical areas. Advanced regression techniques shed light on the intricate relationship between job satisfaction and WFH frequency. The study's critical revelations about regional disparities provide essential perspectives for shaping the future work landscape and informing policy decisions in a post-pandemic world.

KEYWORDS: COVID-19 Impact, Work From Home(WFH), Job Satisfaction, Spatial Analysis

1. Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has dramatically affected labour markets with long-term implications for how, where and when workers conduct their day-to-day tasks. The pandemic forced a rapid organisational shift towards remote work or telecommuting starting from the enforced Work From Home (WFH) regimes affecting a large portion of the workforce thereby reshaping millions' professional and personal lives. This paradigm shift introduced multifaceted challenges, particularly in maintaining work-life balance and ensuring job satisfaction (Bonacini et al., 2021, Clark et al., 2020, Nijp et al., 2016, Gao et al., 2023).

The UK, with its complex socio-economic structure offers a unique context for studying these transformations. Within the current UK research arena, the emphasis predominantly lies on assessing the effects of WFH policies on productivity (Deole et al., 2023) and mental health (Giovanis and Ozdamar, 2022), leaving a notable gap in understanding their impact on job satisfaction, particularly with regard to regional disparities. Furthermore, internationally, such as the research conducted on the implications of WFH in Russia, indicating that from 2016 to 2021, remote workers reported higher job satisfaction than their office-based counterparts. This positive impact persisted both before and during the COVID-19 pandemic, although satisfaction decreased for those working more than eight hours remotely (Smirnykh, 2023). We aim to enrich this field by specifically addressing these overlooked dimensions, specifically how enforced WFH policies affected job satisfaction across different UK regions during the critical 2020 to 2021 period, utilising data from 'Understanding Society, the UK Household Longitudinal Study'.

Delving into regional variations, our study pays special attention to the disparities in job satisfaction across different areas within the UK. Our preliminary findings suggest a stark contrast between regions such as Wales, where a higher level of job satisfaction has been reported, and other areas like London, the South East, the rest of England, and Scotland, where the levels vary significantly. Factors contributing to these regional differences range from the cost of living and work-life balance to

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organisational culture (Jones and Sloane, 2009). By employing advanced regression analysis, we investigate broad trends in job satisfaction, along with regional variations, as a result of the enforced WFH policy during the pandemic.

The following sections will provide an introduction on our data sources, methodological approach, and a case study analysis, all directed towards dissecting the intricate dynamics of job satisfaction during the unique circumstances of the enforced WFH era in various UK regions.

2. Dataset

Our study draw upon data from 'Understanding Society: the UK Household Longitudinal Study,' an annual survey encompassing over 40,000 UK households since 2009, alongside a specific COVID-19 survey conducted between April 2020 and September 2021. This comprehensive panel survey captures a wide array of information across a representative sample of UK households, detailing the social, economic, health, and well-being dynamics of over 100,000 individuals (University of Essex, 2023). The COVID-19 survey, initiated in April 2020 as part of 'Understanding Society,' is designed to explore the pandemic's wide-ranging impacts. This supplemental survey extensively covers health, employment, mental well-being, and social behavior changes during the pandemic, offering a dynamic view of its evolving impact on UK households.

Utilizing data spanning from Wave 11 (2019-2020) to Wave 12 (2020-2021) of the main survey, along with specific COVID-19 survey waves, we gained insights into the UK workforce's employment status, work patterns, and satisfaction levels during the pandemic. This approach enabled us to explore the implications of the enforced WFH policy on job satisfaction across various regions in the UK.

3. Methodology

We employed a robust methodological framework to assess the impact of COVID-19 on job satisfaction, in our analytical approach, we began with descriptive analysis to identify general trends and patterns in job satisfaction among the UK workforces. This initial phase provided an overview of the prevailing levels of satisfaction and highlighted potential areas for more detailed investigation.

To gain deeper insights, we conducted a regression analysis, focusing on exploring the complex relationships between various factors and job satisfaction during the pandemic. The regression model was structured as follows: in constructing the regression model, we incorporated variables from two datasets within 'Understanding Society'. 'Satisfaction with life overall', 'work from home frequency', and 'work hours' were selected from the COVID-19 dataset, while the remaining variables were derived from the main survey dataset.

$$\text{Job Satisfaction} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \times \text{WFH Frequency} + \beta_2 \times \text{COVID period} + \beta_3 \times (\text{WFH Frequency} \times \text{COVID period}) + \beta_4 \times \text{Demographic Factors} + \beta_5 \times \text{Work Factors} + \epsilon$$

Where:

- β_0 is the intercept, representing the baseline level of job satisfaction when all other predictors are zero.
- β_1 represents the effect of WFH frequency on job satisfaction.
- β_2 captures the overall impact of the COVID period on job satisfaction.
- β_3 is the interaction term between WFH frequency and the COVID period, indicating how the relationship between WFH frequency and job satisfaction changes after COVID-19.
- β_4 represents the combined effects of demographic factors such as age and gender.
- β_5 encompasses the influence of work-related factors, including occupation type and commute time.
- ϵ is the error term, accounting for the variation in job satisfaction not explained by the model.

This model allowed us to quantify the influence of key variables on job satisfaction. In particular, it included an interaction term between WFH frequency and the COVID period variable, enabling us to distinguish the specific impact of the pandemic on WFH practices. This COVID period variable is coded

as 0 for the time before the pandemic and 1 for the time during and immediately following the pandemic's outbreak. The demographic factors encapsulated variables such as age, gender and region, while work factors encompassed elements like company size, working hours, commute time, and income satisfaction.

Employing this methodological integration was crucial in isolating the distinct effects of the WFH policy from other contributing factors. It provided a nuanced understanding of the dynamics influencing job satisfaction during this period of significant change in the UK's professional landscape. This comprehensive approach ensured a balanced consideration of both the direct and indirect factors impacting job satisfaction, thereby offering robust and insightful findings relevant to both employers and policymakers.

4. Results

Our research provides a nuanced understanding of job satisfaction in the UK during the COVID-19 pandemic, highlighting the multifaceted impact of remote work and regional disparities.

Contrasting the frequency of WFH and job satisfaction across UK regions, the analysis encapsulated in **Figure 1** highlights the higher WFH frequency in London and the superior job satisfaction levels in Wales. London's darker green on the left suggests a prevalent WFH culture, while the deeper blue in Wales on the right indicates elevated job satisfaction. These observations merit a detailed analysis of Wales and London to understand the factors contributing to these regional differences in work patterns and satisfaction.

Figure 1 Regional Disparities in Job Satisfaction and WFH in the UK: 2019-2021

Figure 2 illustrates the regression analysis results, comparing the impact of various factors on job satisfaction between London and Wales. Solid triangles on the graph signify statistically significant predictors, illustrating their pronounced impact on job satisfaction, while the circles indicate non-significant predictors.

Significant findings indicate a pronounced decline in job satisfaction in Wales during-pandemic, unlike in London, pointing to varied regional impacts of the pandemic. Income satisfaction is identified as a crucial positive determinant of job satisfaction in both regions, highlighting the need to focus on income satisfaction for enhancing job satisfaction. Notably, the positive 'WFH Frequency: COVID period ' interaction in Wales implies that increased WFH has boosted job satisfaction during-pandemic, a

phenomenon not seen in London. These insights underline the importance of tailoring remote working policies to the specific needs and influences in each region.

Figure 2 Comparison of Regression Coefficients for Job Satisfaction Factors in London and Wales

These insights underscore the complex relationship between employment conditions and job satisfaction, with regional context emerging as a pivotal factor. The implications of our findings are profound for policymakers and organisational leaders, advocating for customised strategies that reflect the unique challenges of different regions. For areas where WFH appears to diminish job satisfaction, hybrid working models or job satisfaction initiatives could be instrumental.

5. Conclusion

This study investigates the impact of the shift to WFH practices, prompted by the COVID-19 pandemic, on job satisfaction across the UK. Our research reveals a complex landscape, marked by significant regional differences. Notably, in Wales, a negative correlation is observed between WFH frequency and job satisfaction; yet, this situation evolves during the pandemic. As the frequency of working from home increases, the magnitude of improvement in job satisfaction becomes greater than in the pre-COVID period, reflecting a dynamic shift in the relationship between WFH practices and job satisfaction over time. This positive development in Wales during-pandemic is in stark contrast to the situation in London, where no significant correlation was found between WFH frequency and job satisfaction, either before or after the pandemic.

These findings highlight the intricate relationship between WFH and job satisfaction, revealing that the effects of WFH are not uniformly experienced across different regions. The study underlines the importance of adopting region-specific approaches in formulating remote work policies. It suggests to policymakers and organisational leaders that the efficacy of WFH varies depending on several factors, including regional characteristics and how these areas have adapted post-pandemic.

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Biographies

Chuang Liu, a PhD student at UCL's SpaceTimeLab, focuses on urban work norms post-COVID-19. He completed his MSc in Data Analysis and Human Resource Management at the University of Leeds. His research employs GPS data analysis to probe the interplay between remote work and urban socio-economic patterns.

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